

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE THYROID GLAND IN DIFFUSE TOXIC GOITER

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: to study the main pathomorphological and morphometric structural rearrangements of tissue formations of the thyroid gland (TG) in diffuse toxic goiter (DTG).

Material and methods: the macro- and microscopic structural features of the thyroid gland were studied using the methods of anatomical dissection and histological sections in 15 patients with DTG, both sexes aged from 36 to 60 years old, operated on in the department of general surgery in Chernivtsi.

Results: the analysis of the degree of progression of pathomorphological changes in the tissue and follicular structure of the thyroid revealed a dependence on the duration and severity of the disease. The results of the quantitative study showed that the average diameter of the follicles compared to the norm ($71.8 \pm 0.98 \mu\text{m}$) became larger ($82.3 \pm 1.12 \mu\text{m}$). The height of the follicular epithelium in this pathology was equal to $16.10 \pm 0.12 \mu\text{m}$, in the normal case it was $11.06 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ ($p < 0.01$). This led to a change in Brown's index, i.e., the higher this index was, the lower the functional activity of the organ became.

Conclusion: characteristic morphological features of the thyroid gland in DTG are lymphoplasmacytic infiltration of the stroma of the gland, activation of folliculogenesis, and hyperplasia of the thyroid epithelium, which can lead to the development of functional disorders of the thyroid gland.

Keywords: thyroid gland, diffuse toxic goiter, pathomorphology.

Introduction

In recent years, the physiology and pathology of the thyroid gland (TG) has been separated into an independent discipline - thyrology, which is an important section of endocrinology, due to the wide spread of diseases of this organ and the development of serious complications. In Ukraine, namely in Prykarpattia, which is an endemic region, there is a steady increase in the number of patients with diffuse toxic goiter (DTG), which, according to various data, is from 18% to 62% of the total number of diseases of the endocrine system [3-4].

A number of authors associate the pathomorphological changes that develop in the thyroid gland with the changed environmental situation [4-6]. In numerous review articles and manuals, clinical features, diagnostic issues, pathogenesis, and operative treatment of thyroid diseases are covered in sufficient detail and from different positions [1, 2, 7-9]. Due to the growth of endocrine pathology in Ukraine, our scientists also began to pay quite serious attention to the issue of the pathomorphology of thyroid gland [7, 10]. In recent years, there has been an increase in the frequency of thyroid cancer on the background of TBI, especially in patients over 40 years of age [10-12]. It is known that variants of the normal thyroid hormone activity of the body and the prevalence of thyroid diseases, as some studies have shown, depend on ethnic and climate-geographical factors [4, 5, 13]. However, despite numerous works on the study of DTG, which are mostly based on the results of functional studies, in Ukraine, until now, no detailed pathomorphological study of parenchymal remodeling of the thyroid gland in DTG has been carried out.

The aim of the study.

To give a pathomorphological and morphometric evaluation of the tissue structures of the thyroid gland in DTG based on a complex morphological study

Material and methods.

The object of the study was the thyroid gland (from male and female subjects). The actual material for the study under normal conditions was obtained from 15 people (male and female) who were operated on in the department of general surgery in Chernivtsi. People with diseases of the immune system and endocrine organs were not included in the research material.

The prepared thyroid gland was freed from connective and fatty tissue. Then, from the middle part of each lobe of the gland, a plate with a thickness of 3-4 mm across was cut out for its further histological study. The iron together with the tags (data of the patients) were placed in gauze bags and dipped in a 10% solution of neutral formalin. The fixed material was embedded in paraffin. Sections with a thickness of 5-6 μm were stained with Ehrlich's hematoxylin, eosin and van Gieson's picrofuchsin.

Along with studying the drugs, we measured the diameter of the follicles and the height of their epithelial lining and vessels of the microcirculatory channel using an ocular micrometer. Measurements were made in 90 follicles in each thyroid gland. The mean internal diameter of the follicles was determined by dividing the sum of the largest and smallest diameters in half. To establish the average height of the glandular epithelium, the height of the lining cells of each measured follicle was measured. Brown's index was calculated by dividing the average diameter of the follicle by the average height of the follicular epithelium. To evaluate the results of pathomorphological studies, a system of

computer analysis of microscopic images, consisting of a light-optical microscope, was used.

The results of the study were processed by the methods of variational statistics with the calculation of average values and their standard deviation. Analysis of variance was performed for independent samples using the Mann-Whitney U-test. The null hypothesis was rejected at $p < 0.04$.

Results and their discussion.

Histological studies of the thyroid gland in individuals of the control group (normal) showed that in the mature age of the second period, the histological structure of the thyroid gland corresponds to that described in the literature. The parenchyma of the organ consists of follicles of various sizes - from large to small, between which there are layers of connective tissue and fields of interfollicular epithelium. The connective tissue layer of the gland is divided into lobes: blood vessels - arterioles, capillaries and venules - lie in the interlobular space. The walls of the follicles are separated from the adjacent tissue by a basal membrane, on which a single-row follicular epithelium is located. Follicles are filled with colloid, the metachromasia of which indicates active processes of functional metabolism between it and thyrocytes.

On the histological preparations of the thyroid gland, in which operations were performed for DTG, the connective tissue fibers in the stroma of the gland were impregnated with pale edematous contents, they were loosened, and large lymphoid infiltration centers were found in the interfollicular connective tissue. Histologically, thyroid follicles were usually irregular in shape, instead of the normal single-layer cubic epithelium, their walls were lined with cylindrical, often multi-layered epithelium. The latter contained a small amount of liquid, colorless colloid with many vacuoles.

The most characteristic morphological feature of DTG is lymphoplasmacytic infiltration [14, 15]. According to our data, diffuse lymphoplasmacytic infiltration usually prevailed over lymphoid. Lymphocytes not only contacted follicles, but also penetrated the cytoplasm of acinar cells, which is not observed in normal thyroid. The same picture can be given by large lymphoid follicles, which can always be found in the thyroid stroma in this pathology.

In these cases, papillary proliferation does not occupy the entire gland diffusely, but is located in individual cells. A number of authors [14,15] believe that hyperplastic processes in the thyroid epithelium (papillary proliferation of the epithelium and neoplasms of follicles) are characteristic morphological signs of DTG. Proliferation of the epithelium is characterized by the formation of papillary growths in the lumen of the follicles. Papillae in the follicle are represented by folds of epithelium. without a connective tissue base. There are short and wide papillae with a capillary in the connective tissue stroma, covered with thyroid epithelium.

Hyperplastic processes in DTG are manifested by neoplasms of small oval or rounded follicles. In addition to hyperplasia of the follicular epithelium, there is also hyperplasia of the extrafollicular epithelium. At

the same time, thyroid islands of epithelium appear between the follicles. The functional activity of the cells leads to the accumulation of colloid, the further development of the process ends with the formation of new small follicles, pressed into the lumen of the follicles - Sanderson's pads.

Sanderson's pads on the side of the follicles are covered with a higher prismatic epithelium, which indicates an increase in the functional activity of the cells. Against the background of pronounced diffuse proliferation of the follicular epithelium in the tissue of the gland, the formation of nodes with increased activity of thyrocytes is noted. The cause of nodulation is uneven proliferative processes in the thyroid epithelium. The stroma is compacted, focal lymphocytic infiltrates are defined in it, up to the formation of lymphatic follicles.

The index of colloid accumulation (Brown's index), which is derived from two main indicators (the average diameter of the lumen of the follicles and the height of the epithelium), most closely reflects the degree of activity of the thyroid gland. As follows from the results of the quantitative study, the average diameter of the follicles compared to the norm ($70.8 \pm 1.19 \mu\text{m}$) became larger ($808 \pm 126 \mu\text{m}$). The height of the follicular epithelium in this pathology was equal to $15.16 \pm 0.22 \mu\text{m}$, in the normal case it was $10.06 \pm 0.09 \mu\text{m}$ ($p < 0.01$). This caused changes in the Brownian index, i.e. the higher this index, the lower the functional activity of the organ. The data we obtained on the general dynamics of the colloid accumulation index completely coincide with the data of other authors [9, 16]. With diffuse goiter, sympathetic mediation is suppressed, i.e. a decrease in adrenergic mediation in the body, which is accompanied by a decrease in the functional activity of the thyroid gland. This leads to a decrease in iodine content compared to a normal gland [1, 2, 4].

Conclusion.

The obtained set of pathomorphological data in DTG indicates the presence of hyperplastic processes (hyperplasia of the thyroid epithelium, activation of folliculogenesis and lymphoid infiltration). The results should be taken into account when developing methods of prevention, treatment and pathomorphological diagnosis of thyroid disease.

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